

Grain quality

Physical and milling characters of popular Maruteru rice varieties

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We evaluated the physical and milling characters of eight rainfed lowland rice varieties commonly grown in Andhra Pradesh and parts of Maharashtra,

Karnataka, and Orissa, India. Sampling was done 1 mo after harvest; grain had 14% moisture content.

The 1,000-grain weight of Vijetha was heaviest (see table). All have medium-shaped grain and medium-length grain, extra for Vijetha, which has long grain.

The brown rice recovery was higher for MTU4870 and Krishnaveni compared with other varieties. The milled rice recovery was highest for MTU4870.

The bran and germ percentage for Nandi was highest (10.1) followed by that for Krishnaveni (9.4) and Chaitanya (9.1). Among these varieties, head rice recovery was highest in MTU4870. Except for Swarna and Chaitanya, all other varieties yielded more than the acceptable head rice recovery of 60% (see table). Broken rice were lowest in Vijetha (3.4%) and highest in Swarna (7.6%). ■

Physical and milling characters of popular rice varieties. Agricultural Research Station, Maruteru, India. 1995.

Variety	Physical characters					Milling characters (%)							
	Duration (d)	Grain length (mm)	Grain breadth (mm)	Grain thickness (mm)	L-B ratio	Grain length	Grain shape	1000-grain weight (g)	Brown rice	Bran and germ	Milled rice recovery	Broken rice	Head rice recovery
Swarna MTU7029	150	5.77	2.24	1.72	2.57	Medium	Medium	19.90	75.50	8.90	66.60	7.61	58.99
Pratibha MTU5293	165	6.35	2.16	1.70	2.94	Medium	Medium	20.60	74.50	6.30	68.20	4.30	63.90
Vajram MTU5249	150	6.13	2.31	1.71	2.64	Medium	Medium	21.10	76.60	7.40	69.20	5.22	63.98
Nandi MTU5182	150	6.10	2.25	1.75	2.72	Medium	Medium	21.10	76.70	10.10	66.60	5.50	61.10
Chaitanya MTU2067	150	5.81	2.35	1.62	2.46	Medium	Medium	20.90	70.70	9.10	61.60	6.50	55.10
Krishnaveni MTU2077	150	5.69	2.24	1.72	2.54	Medium	Medium	20.20	77.10	9.40	67.70	5.40	62.30
Vijetha MTU 1001	140	6.63	2.37	1.85	2.80	Long	Medium	27.50	74.50	8.70	65.80	3.40	62.40
MTU4870	150	5.88	2.28	1.79	2.57	Medium	Medium	22.00	77.20	6.30	70.90	4.60	66.30
X		6.05	2.28	1.73	2.67			21.60	75.38	8.28	67.08	5.32	61.76
SD		0.32	0.07	0.07	0.15			2.44	2.17	1.44	2.75	1.31	3.45
CV		5.34	2.98	3.89	5.74			4.50	2.88	17.34	4.10	24.56	5.58

Variability of quality indices in aromatic rice germplasm

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Aromatic rice varieties are generally preferred over nonaromatic types and therefore earn premium prices. Among the aromatics, those with long slender grains (length >6.5 mm and breadth <2.0 mm) and high lengthwise volume expansion after cooking are popularly called basmati rice. These varieties have helped countries such as India, Pakistan, and Thailand earn considerable foreign exchange.

We evaluated 356 traditional aromatic rice varieties for eight grain and

cooking characteristics: amylose content (AC), gelatinization temperature (GT) as indicated by the alkali spreading score, gel consistency (GC), milled rice kernel length (KL), kernel breadth (KB), kernel length-breadth ratio (L/B), kernel elongation after cooking (KE) (length of cooked rice divided by

original kernel length using the average of 10 unbroken milled rice kernels), and 1,000-grain weight (WT).

Wide variation was observed for all the characteristics, with the maximum being for GC followed by WT and AC. Most of the aromatic varieties from India, Myanmar, Nepal, and Pakistan

Table 1. Varieties (no.) in different groups based on quality indices.

Quality index	Very low	Low	Intermediate	High
Amylose content (%)	2.5-9.0	9.0-20.0	20.1-25.0	>25.0
	27	169	155	5
Gelatinization temperature (Alkali spreading score)	6&7	-	4 & 5	1&3
	54		273	29
Gel consistency (mm)	-	0-40	41-60	>60
		77	148	131
Kernel elongation	1.31-1.60	1.61-1.80	1.81-2.0	>2.0
	66	100	101	69
Length-breadth ratio	1.3-2.0	2.01-3.0	3.01-4.0	>4.01
	44	140	159	13

possess intermediate AC, GT, and GC. WT, one of the key selection indices for high grain yield, ranged from 7.5 to 42.2 g. Milled rice KL ranged from 3.20 to 8.06 mm, and KB ranged from very thin (1.38 mm) to very thick (3.08) mm. Based on the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations' milled rice scale, the varieties were grouped as long-slender (110), medium-slender (9), long-bold (82), medium-bold (19), short-bold (33), short-round (42), and medium (63).

High volume expansion after cooking (maximum linear KE with minimum breadthwise expansion) is one of the characters of basmati rice. Varieties that double their length with cooking are preferred. KE range was wide among the varieties (Table 1).

We determined the Pearson's correlation coefficients for eight quality

indices. AC showed highly significant negative correlation with all the traits except LB (0.10) and KE (0.19). WT had significant negative correlation with AC and KE, suggesting that lower grain weight types must be selected to identify basmati types. The association between KE and KL as well as LB was negative and significant, indicating that many of the slender grains do not

elongate after cooking. KE had a significant positive association with AC, while that with GT was significant and negative. Most of the aromatic varieties with greater linear KE also have intermediate AC and GT.

Among the aromatic germplasm evaluated, 39 accessions are basmati based on grain shape and elongation; details are provided for nine (Table 2). ■

Table 2. Some typical Basmati varieties and their grain and cooking quality characteristics.^a

Variety	Origin	AC	GT	GC	KL	KB	LB	KE
Barah	Afghanistan	17.6	4.58	70	7.55	1.88	4.02	2.18
MussaTarom	Iran	19.2	4.20	40	7.62	1.88	4.05	1.83
Mulai	Iran	19.5	3.58	55	7.76	1.96	3.96	1.93
Sadri	Iran	18.2	4.54	35	7.66	1.94	3.45	2.10
Pakistani Fine	Pakistan	20.4	5.40	50	6.96	1.96	3.55	1.93
Sathi Basmati	India	18.4	3.83	58	7.24	1.92	3.78	1.95
Basmati 370	India	21.0	3.83	57	6.84	1.84	3.72	2.10
KarnalLocal	India	21.2	3.66	60	7.06	1.90	3.72	1.85
Hansraj	India	18.1	4.50	60	6.88	1.94	3.55	2.17

^a AC = amylose content, GT = gelatinization temperature, GC = gel consistency, KL = kernel length, KB = kernel breadth, LB = length-breadth ratio, KE = kernel elongation.

Biochemical composition of principal components of rice seeds

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Rice is an important source of carbohydrates in the diets of several Nigerian populations, especially in the forest belt. We determined the nutritional

values of rough rice, unpolished rice, polished rice, hulls, bran, and rice mill feed for rice grown in Nigeria.

Rice components were collected from the rice mill of the College of Agriculture, Enugu State University, Abakaliki Campus, Nigeria, ground, and then mixed to obtain homogeneous samples. The methods of the Association of Official Analytical Chemists were used to determine moisture,

crude protein, ash, crude fiber, crude fat, dry matter, and nitrogen free extract. Calorific values were calculated by multiplying the mean values of crude protein, fat, fiber, and nitrogen free extracts by Atwater factors.

The mineral composition was assayed for each sample in 5 N HCl and then analyzed with a Perkin-Elmer atomic absorption spectrophotometer and flame photometry method.

Chemical composition of the principal nutritional components of rice grown in Nigeria.

Constituent	Composition (%) ^a						
	Rough rice	Unpolished rice	Polished rice	Rice hulls	Rice bran	Rice mill feed	Rice starch refuse
<i>Proximate composition (n=3)</i>							
Moisture	12.3 ± 0.4	12.3 ± 0.2	10.8 ± 0.1	11.4 ± 0.2	11.2 ± 0.2	6.1 ± 0.3	9.1 ± 1.0
Dry matter	87.7 ± 0.1	87.8 ± 0.4	89.2 ± 0.7	88.6 ± 0.4	88.9 ± 0.5	93.9 ± 3.3	90.9 ± 0.2
Ash	6.4 ± 0.2	2.1 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.1	17.2 ± 1.0	10.8 ± 0.3	15.9 ± 2.8	2.1 ± 0.1
Crude protein	9.6 ± 0.0	9.1 ± 0.6	8.4 ± 0.4	3.4 ± 0.2	12.0 ± 0.4	6.9 ± 1.2	9.9 ± 0.9
Crude fat	1.7 ± 0.5	1.1 ± 0.1	1.0 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.2	15.1 ± 0.4	4.8 ± 0.7	0.9 ± 0.0
Crude fiber	11.1 ± 0.8	0.5 ± 0.5	0.2 ± 0.0	34.7 ± 1.6	8.7 ± 1.2	27.9 ± 6.8	1.9 ± 0.0
Nitrogen free extract	58.9 ± 1.8	75.0 ± 1.0	78.1 ± 0.4	32.7 ± 1.1	42.2 ± 1.5	38.5 ± 4.5	78.2 ± 0.9
Calorific value (kcal 100 g ⁻¹)	334.1	348.5	355.2	288.5	387.6	336.2	388.1
<i>Mineral content (n=3)</i>							
Calcium	0.1 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0
Phosphorus	0.3 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	1.7 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.0

^aValues are means ± standard deviations of three replications.